

STIGMATIZATION OF MENTAL ILLNESS AND HELP-SEEKING BEHAVIOR AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS IN TURKEY

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INTRODUCTION

Stigmatization of mental illness refers to great disapproval for people suffering from mental illnesses which may lead to marginalization and exclusion from society (Avdibegović–Hasanović, 2017: 931). Even though people suffering from mental illnesses are the primary target of stigmatization, effects of stigmatization of mental illness cannot be limited to the people suffering from those illnesses (Mazumder-Thompson-Hodgetts, 2019). Prevalence of mental disorders vary between 9.6-27.8% in adult population (Moffitt et al., 2010: 899; & Corrigan, 2018:587). Most common conditions for young adults include major depressive disorder and generalized anxiety disorder (Kessler et al., 2005: 5). Latest report of World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that approximately 25% of global population has suffered from at least one psychiatric condition in their lifetime (Grisales-Romero, et al., 2020:29). However, people in need for psychiatric care either do not seek for care or do not complete their treatment plan suggested by medical professionals (Corrigan et al., 2001:187). Latest estimations indicate that at least 60% of patients suffering from mental illnesses do not receive adequate treatment which is mostly attributable to stigmatization of mental illnesses (WHO, 2001).

Stigmatization of mental illnesses vary with race, nationality, educational status and age of the focus group. Studies in Turkish population revealed that female participants with younger age or higher socioeconomic status exhibited higher stigmatization towards mental conditions (Gur & Kucuk, 2016: e22267). Studies investigating mental health stigma among college students revealed higher rates among Japanese college students compared to their American peers (Masuda et al. 2009:178). Utilization of mental health services is inversely correlated with the degree of stigma in the society as shown by lower utilization of mental health services by Asian Americans, a society with higher stigmatization rates,

compared to Caucasians (Loya et al. 2010: 484). Despite high rates of psychiatric disorders during young adulthood and growing focus over stigmatization, studies on this field are limited. Turkey has a relatively young population with approximately 39% under age 25 according to latest estimates compared to most western countries (Coşkun et al. 2017: 323).

In this study, our aim is to investigate the self-reported stigmatization of mental conditions and help-seeking behavior regarding psychiatric conditions among young college students in Turkey, and its correlates.

METHODS

Sampling

This study was designed as a cross-sectional survey performed among Arel University students in Turkey between February and May 2019 and approved by Ethics Committee of Arel University. Participants (n=460) are full-time undergraduate or graduate students from different departments with ages varying between 18 and 25.

Instruments

In this study a standardized survey is utilized which comprised of demographic information and 22 statements about possible conditions regarding our topic of interest including social interactions, professional life, treatment options and their efficiency, social isolation and social support which participants may agree or disagree (Five-point Likert scale is used containing “strongly disagree”, “disagree”, “neither agree or disagree”, “agree” and “strongly agree” for assessment). Questionnaires are created in accordance with few large-scale surveys after adjustment into Turkish population and expert opinion while no pilot study has previously been performed with such survey (Lipson, et al.2018: 348; McCormack, et al. 2018: 1342). Questionnaires include questions from the listed studies that are adjusted to the demographics of the study population while few questions are discarded following the consensus of all authors. We are unable to test the validity of the survey nor the individual sections of the survey to the lack of standardized study group and lack of previous studies conducted on similar

population. Each question is analyzed independently without any total score. Results of Likert-scale outcomes have been analyzed. Participants were contacted in person in the university campus and all participants were required to provide informed consent before being part of our study. Responses were anonymous and participation to our study was based on voluntariness. Questions and statements in the survey are prepared to assess the attitudes of college students towards mentally ill people and assess their help-seeking behaviour in case of any psychiatric condition.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed by using statistical software SPSS version 25.0 Demographic background of the participants in terms of age, gender and university department were assessed. Five-point Likert scale responses were graded between 1 and 5 in which more appropriate answers were graded with higher points. Descriptive statistical analysis for each section and statement were performed individually in accordance with the age and departments of the participants. Responses of participants from different departments, grades and genders are compared by using t-test. Due to variations in the syllabus of university education in Turkey t-test was preferred in the statistical analysis with grades. The alpha error was set at $p < .05$.

RESULTS

General characteristics of the participants and general information regarding their medical and psychiatric history are reviewed at Table 1. On average 1% of the participants had preferred not to disclose their answers regarding those issues. Analysis of help-seeking behavior regarding psychological issues demonstrated that approximately 30% of the participants would not consider professional psychological help even if they believed they had any psychological conditions while 33.4% preferred not to share with their friends if they seek for psychiatric help. Details are given at Table 1. Correlation analysis of the help-seeking behavior regarding mental conditions revealed no statistically significant difference with age ($p > .05$). No statistically significant differences had been observed between students from psychology department and rest by using correlation analysis ($p > .05$). Additionally, 77.5% of the responders believed that significant prejudice about psychiatric conditions

and people using psychiatric medications were present in the society. Participants did not consider all kinds of psychiatric medications similarly while attention-enhancing drugs and anti-depressants were considered as “most innocent” psychiatric medications.

Self-reported stigmatization behaviors towards people with mental health conditions were significant among our population as 42% stated that they might prefer putting distance to their friends if they learn that their friends have any psychiatric condition while 45% of the participants preferred not to be friends or be at the same working environment with a person having any psychiatric condition. Details are given at Table 1. Furthermore, 53.5% of the population did not believe that severe psychiatric conditions could not be treated with today’s medical capabilities.

Correlation analysis demonstrated no statistically significant difference between males and females in terms of admission to psychology / psychiatry services or use of psychiatric medications ($p > .05$) while statistically very significant difference was present in terms of self-reported stigmatization behavior ($p < .01$). Females had higher degree of self-reported stigmatization behaviors compared to males. No statistically significant difference in help-seeking behaviors had been observed among genders.

Students with a major in psychology department had lower self-reported stigmatization behavior compared to students from other departments in a statistically very significant manner ($p < .01$) and considered psychiatric conditions more treatable in a statistically significant fashion ($p < .05$). On the other hand, students from psychology department were more reluctant to seek for psychological or psychiatric help compared to others ($p < .05$). No correlation between the university department and self-reported stigmatization-related attitudes has been determined.

Correlation analysis revealed no statistically significant difference between students from 1st-2nd grade compared to 3rd-4th grade in any statements ($p > .05$) in terms of help-seeking behavior or self-reported stigmatization of mental illnesses.

DISCUSSION

Stigmatization of mental illness and negative perceptions about mentally ill patients are highlighted topics in the field of psychiatry. Even though psychiatric conditions are commonly encountered during young adulthood period, studies investigating stigmatization are limited in number and extent. According to large-scale studies approximately 51% of people from developed countries conceive mental illnesses similar to physical illnesses while only 7-8% believed that people with mental diseases were more violent and aggressive compared to others. Although higher rates of stigmatization are reported in developing countries, we report self-reported stigmatization attitude rates over 50% on multiple aspects among college students (Seeman et al. 2016: 115).

Improvement of stigma-related behaviors after psychiatry internship among medical students and lower degrees of stigma-related behaviors among students with a relative with mental illness illustrate the importance of education and knowledge in the emergence of stigmatization (Poreddi et al. 2015: 349). Similarly, we report lower stigma rates among students with a major in psychology compared to other departments. Sociocultural factors are considered as one of the predominant factor leading to emergence of stigmatization as shown by differences in stigmatization among medical professionals with different nationality (Adewuya & Oguntade, 2007: 931). Also, our findings suggest higher degree of self-reported stigmatization in females, concurrent with the literature, while effect of age and grade are insignificant. Though, our study is primarily limited by involving patients from restricted age range.

Help-seeking behavior regarding psychiatric conditions are on rise in young adults and adolescents leading to increased psychiatric diagnosis rates and medication use. Despite studies indicating differences in the literature, our findings suggest no difference in help-seeking behavior among college students with grade or gender (Eisenberg et al, 2009: 522). We detected lower rates of help-seeking behavior in students from psychology department. In general, our study population demonstrates higher rates of self-reported stigmatization attitudes which may be related to cultural and social differences in Turkish society including common negative beliefs and misconceptualization of people with mental illnesses. Possible reasoning includes cultural differences, spiritual beliefs about

psychiatric conditions, role of media, misbeliefs about mentally ill patients and psychiatric medications in the society and lack of adequate school education regarding psychology.

As a solution, we recommend educational interventions providing clear and accurate information about psychiatric conditions, appropriate use of media including television series and news, spending time with people suffering from mental illnesses as a social work and anti-stigma campaigns. Effectiveness of those methods have been demonstrated in multiple studies (Rainone, et al. 2018: 267; Sharma et al.2020:33, DuPaul et al. 2014:23). Thus, we highly recommend and advocate for the implementation of those measures which may enhance help-seeking behavior and result in higher quality treatment for people in need.

Ethics Committee Approval: The study was approved by Ethics Committee of Arel University.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declared no conflicts of interest.

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Table 1: General characteristics of the participants included in the study and their responses regarding self-reported stigmatization behavior

General characteristics of the participants	Results
Total number (n)	460
Response rate	55%
Mean age	22.0 ± 2.1
Gender	114 Males (24.7%) 346 Female (75.3%)
Departments in the university	Nutrition and dietetics (n=30, 6.52%) Child development (75, 16.3%) Physiotherapy (22, 4.78%), Nursing school (79, 17.1%), Psychology (115, 25%) Health management (72, 15.6%) Social services students (66, 14.3%) Public relation (n=1)
Prior admission to a psychologist	25.2%
Prior admission to a psychiatrist	16.7% (96.7% with prescribed medication)
Outcome of need for psychiatry admission	33.4% preferred not to share with friends 65% preferred not to use medications if prescribed 85% preferred not to share with friends if use medication
Outcome of a person with psychiatric diagnosis	42% preferred putting distance 45% preferred not to become friend 81% advocated strict control over that person 62% advocated isolation of that person from others at hospital setting